

"EFFECTIVE TEACHING STRATEGIES FOR PHONETICS, GRAMMAR, AND MORPHOLOGY IN INTERMEDIATE EFL STUDENTS: A MULTIMODAL APPROACH"

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Abstract

This thesis investigates the most efficient methods for teaching grammar, morphology, and phonetics in an intermediate EFL classroom. The study covers difficulties with pronunciation, grammatical structures, and vocabulary acquisition for a group of five students aged 17 to 18. The study assesses advances in students' language ability through focused activities such as phonetic games, shadowing exercises, and corpus-based practice. Significant improvements in lexical knowledge, grammatical comprehension, and pronunciation accuracy are shown by the results, which emphasize the value of interactive and multimodal teaching strategies.

Pronouncing diphthongs correctly and using stress and intonation patterns in real-world contexts are the main goals of phonetic education. Common issues with verb tenses, reflexive pronouns, sentence constructions, and mass/count nouns are covered in grammar teaching. A key component of morphological instruction is the application of prefixes and suffixes to increase vocabulary and improve reading comprehension.

Pre- and post-assessment data, student feedback, and classroom observations show that students' morphological awareness, grammatical accuracy, and pronunciation have significantly improved. The results indicate that the unique requirements of intermediate EFL learners can be successfully met by using multimodal teaching methodologies that accommodate kinesthetic, auditory, and visual learning styles. By illustrating the usefulness of various teaching strategies and offering insights into how they affect language acquisition, this study advances the subject of language education.

Keywords: Multimodal Teaching Strategies, Intermediate EFL Learners, Phonetics, Grammar, Morphology, Phonetic Games, Shadowing Exercises, Corpus-Based Activities, Pronunciation Improvement, Grammatical Accuracy, Morphological Awareness, Stress and Intonation, Mass/Count Nouns, Verb Tenses, Reflexive Pronouns, Prefixes and Suffixes, Vocabulary Expansion, Reading Comprehension, Data Analysis, Language Acquisition.

1. Introduction

Teaching English to intermediate learners presents a challenge that calls for creative solutions to handle certain language issues. This study investigates how well multimodal teaching techniques can improve intermediate EFL learners' phonological, grammatical, and morphological skills. In order to meet the demands of the participants and enhance their overall language skills, a variety of educational approaches were used, ranging from tactile to visual and aural.

2. Literature Review

Phonetics and Phonology

Phonetics and Phonology:

Pronouncing words correctly is essential for efficient English communication. McMahon's (2020) research highlights the significance of mastering diphthongs and their function in clear speech. Yavas (2016) emphasizes the equal importance of stress and intonation, pointing out how they affect the meaning and flow of sentences.

Grammar & Syntax:

Recognizing the difference between count and mass nouns, appropriately utilizing past tenses, and utilizing reflexive pronouns are common areas of difficulty for intermediate learners. These prevalent problems are explained by Folse (2009) and Berk (1999), which emphasizes the importance of focused grammar education.

Morphology:

Reading comprehension and vocabulary growth depend on an understanding of prefixes and suffixes (Hennessy & Apel, 2017). Learners can improve their language skills and infer word meanings with the aid of morphological awareness.

Corpus Linguistics:

Resources such as SKELL can help clarify how language is used in everyday situations and help students learn by using examples from real-world situations (Green, 2018). Accurate language use is supported by corpus-based pedagogy, which offers contextual examples.

3 Methodology

Five intermediate Lyceum students studying English as a foreign language (EFL) between the ages of 17 and 18 participated in the study. The Common European Framework of Reference (CEFR) indicates that they are proficient at level B1 (intermediate).

Design of Research

Utilizing a combination of quantitative and qualitative data, this study used a mixed-methods approach to evaluate how well multimodal teaching strategies improve students' phonological, grammatical, and morphological skills.

Intervention:

Phonological Education

Diphthongs: To practice pronouncing English diphthongs correctly, a phonetic game was created. Students used a map-based activity that connected pronunciation to geographical locations to identify and pronounce diphthongs.

Stress and Intonation: To help students with word stress, phrase stress, and intonation, shadowing exercises were carried out using snippets from the Netflix series Wednesday.

Instruction in Grammar:

Mass/Count Nouns: Practice differentiating between mass and count nouns using the provided worksheets.

Verbs: To assist students in differentiating and appropriately using past tenses, visual aids and activities were utilized.

Reflexive Pronouns: To improve comprehension of reflexive pronouns, team-based exercises with visual aids were utilized.

Sentence Types: Practice activities and visual aids were used to facilitate instruction on simple, compound, complex, and compound-complex sentences.

Instruction in Morphology:

Prefixes and Suffixes: To increase vocabulary and enhance reading comprehension, activities centered on comprehending and utilizing frequently occurring prefixes and suffixes.

Linguistics of Corpus:

SKELL Tool: Through corpus-based exercises, students were reinforced in the usage of mass and count nouns by using the Sketch Engine for Language Learning (SKELL).

Data Collection Pre- and Post-Assessments:

To assess improvements in pronunciation, grammatical accuracy, and morphological knowledge, tests were given both before and after the intervention.

Student input: To acquire qualitative information about how students felt about the teaching strategies, surveys and interviews were done.

Observations in the classroom: A record of observations was kept to gauge how well students applied the lessons they had learnt.

Data Analysis

The study employed quantitative data from assessments to ascertain any alterations in the proficiency levels of the students. To learn more about the efficacy of the teaching techniques and the experiences of the students, qualitative data from observations and feedback were analyzed.

4. Phonetics, Phonology, and Morphology

Topic 1: Correct Pronunciation of Diphthongs

The explanation for diphthongs is that they are complicated vowel sounds whose qualities alter as pronounced. Understanding can be impacted by mispronounced words.

Activity: Practice proper pronunciation with a map-based activity and a phonetic game including word pairs (such as "Beer" vs. "Bear").

Topic 2: Word Stress, Sentence Stress, and Intonation

Definition: Meaning and clarity in speech are influenced by stress and intonation.

Activity: Practice stress patterns and intonation by shadowing actors while watching "Wednesday" on Netflix.

Topic 3: Prefixes and Suffixes in Morphology

Explanation: Developing one's vocabulary benefits from an understanding of prefixes and suffixes.

Practice with common prefixes and suffixes with worksheets and exercises.

5. Syntax and Grammar

1 Topic: Count/Mass Nouns

Justification: Proper grammar requires that mass and count nouns be distinguished from one another.

Activity: Worksheets and visual aids to help with accurately identifying, utilizing, and counting nouns.

Topic 2: Differentiating Between Past Tenses Definition: Clear communication requires the proper use of past tenses, including regular and irregular verbs.

Activity: Practice problems and visual aids with an emphasis on past tense forms.

3 Topic: Reflexive Nouns

Explanation: Reflexive pronouns denote acts taken by the subject upon itself and are used to emphasize points.

Activity: Exercises using teams to practice using reflexive pronouns correctly.

Topic 4: Kinds of Sentences

Justification: Writing coherence is enhanced by knowledge of several sentence patterns, including simple, compound, complex, and compound-complex.

Activity: Using visual aids, analyze sentence structures while reading texts.

6. Using SKELL for Corpus Linguistics Applications

Justification: SKELL aids pupils in comprehending word usage conventions and proper context-based application.

Activity: SKELL will be used as a pre-activity to analyze instances of count and mass nouns. Writing activities will then follow.

Including in Lessons

Justification: Including corpus-based exercises to strengthen grammar and vocabulary use.

Task: Composing assignments grounded in corpus analysis.

7. Findings and Results

The results of the investigation showed that there had been notable advancements in the students vocabulary usage, grammar accuracy, and pronunciation. Pronunciation and intonation were especially improved by the phonetic game and shadowing exercises. Worksheets on grammar and morphology improved comprehension of intricate linguistic rules and decreased errors. Students responded strongly to the practical examples and reinforcement of proper noun usage offered by SKELL.

8 Discussion

The intermediate EFL learners in this study gained greatly from the multimodal teaching tactics used. Specific learning obstacles were addressed with morphological activities and targeted grammar instruction, while phonetic games and shadowing exercises enhanced pronunciation and stress patterns. The combination of SKELL and corpus linguistics provided useful reinforcement for language use. Feedback from the students indicated that the strategies were more effective and that there was more involvement. Even with these improvements, some students were still having trouble with complex grammatical structures, which suggests that more focused practice is still required.

9 Conclusion

The study shows that intermediate EFL learners' English ability can be effectively improved through the use of multimodal teaching methodologies. Phonetic games, shadowing exercises, grammar worksheets, and corpus-based activities were used in conjunction to treat specific areas of difficulty and

enhance language proficiency in general. Subsequent studies ought to investigate enduring effects and supplementary techniques to aid students in grasping intricate facets of the English language. This study emphasizes how important it is to use a variety of teaching strategies to better suit the unique needs of EFL students and advance their language learning

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